

PERFORMANCE OF E-NAM IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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MS Received: 03.08.2024; MS Revised:28.04.2024; MS Accepted:29.08.2024)

MS 3232

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRI-BUSINESS MANAGEMENT,)

Abstract

The e-NAM (electronic National Agricultural Market) is a pioneering initiative aimed at integrating India's fragmented agricultural markets by connecting traditional APMC mandis into a cohesive national network. This study rigorously assesses e-NAM's impact and performance in Nagpur District, focusing on data collected from 80 farmers and 20 traders for the financial year 2023-24. The findings underscore e-NAM's effectiveness in advancing market transparency and efficiency, offering significant benefits such as streamlined transactions and improved market access. Despite this progress, the study identifies a gap in detailed understanding of the platform, particularly among farmers, alongside major constraints such as elevated transportation costs, subpar infrastructure, and apprehension towards digital transactions. Logistic regression analysis reveals that factors such as social category, education level, and proximity to APMC facilities positively affect farmers' willingness to engage with e-NAM, whereas age and distance from the APMC negatively influence their adoption. Traders face additional challenges including technological illiteracy and high transportation expenses, further impeding their participation. The study highlights the substantial potential of e-NAM to enhance market efficiency but also emphasizes the need for targeted improvements in infrastructure, education, and support systems to foster greater adoption and realize the full benefits of this transformative platform.

Keywords: e-NAM; APMC; e-trading; digital payment; awareness; willingness to participate; logistic regression technique; garret ranking technique; guttman scaling technique

Introduction and Objectives

The transformation of agricultural markets through digital platforms has the potential to revolutionize the sector, enhancing efficiency, transparency, and market access for farmers and traders alike. Among the various digital initiatives in Indian agriculture, the electronic National Agriculture Market (e-NAM) stands out as a significant endeavor aimed at modernizing agricultural trade. Launched by the Government of India in 2016, e-NAM seeks to create a unified national market for agricultural commodities by integrating existing Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) yards across the country into a single online platform. This initiative is designed to provide farmers with better market access, improve price discovery, and reduce transactional inefficiencies.

The Nagpur district of Maharashtra, a significant agricultural hub, presents an intriguing case for evaluating the performance and impact of e-NAM. This district, known for its diverse agricultural produce, including pulses, oilseeds, and fruits, has witnessed a gradual shift towards digital trading platforms. However, the extent to which e-NAM has effectively addressed the challenges faced by local farmers and traders remains an area of considerable interest.

Despite the potential benefits of e-NAM, its implementation has encountered various challenges. Issues such as inadequate infrastructure, technological illiteracy, and resistance to change have been reported, impacting the system's efficiency and acceptance. Understanding these challenges in the context of Nagpur district is crucial for assessing the performance of e-NAM and identifying areas for improvement.

This research paper aims to evaluate the performance of e-NAM in Nagpur district, focusing on the awareness about e-Nam among the farmers, the willingness of farmers and traders to participate in e-Nam, and constraints faced by both farmers and traders in adopting and utilizing the platform. By employing Logistic regression model and Garret's ranking technique, this study will analyze the key issues reported by stakeholders and assess the impact of e-NAM on market operations and outcomes. The findings will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of e-NAM in addressing market inefficiencies and suggest actionable recommendations for enhancing its performance.

In doing so, this study contributes to the broader discourse on digital agricultural markets and offers evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to optimize the benefits of e-NAM and similar digital platforms in rural and agricultural settings. The specific objectives of the study are:

To study the awareness about e-NAM concept and benefits among the farmers in Nagpur District.

To study the willingness of farmers and traders to participate in e-NAM.

To examine the constraints perceived by farmer and trader in adoption of e-NAM.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was conducted in Nagpur district of Maharashtra during 2023-24. Kalmana APMC was chosen on purpose since it was the only APMC who was integrated with the e-NAM system. The survey included 80 farmers and 20 traders from Kalmana APMC. The respondent for the study was operationally defined as the farmers who registered and traded with e-NAM in Kalmana APMC of Nagpur. The primary data were collected personally with the help of Survey schedules; the interviews were conducted in farmer's fields or in their homes through face-to-face contact.

Guttman Scaling Analysis:

The technique used was Guttman Scaling also sometimes known as cumulative scaling or Scalogram Analysis. Here in the analysis, the awareness level among the farmers and traders were recognized using Guttman scale. A single dimensional set of question/statement were prepared, these questions were asked regarding working of e-NAM completely.

Logit Regression Analysis

To study the willingness, Logit regression analysis was attempted to understand the willingness of farmers and traders to predict the probability of an event happening for an individual.

The logistic regression equation can be represented as: -

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \ln \frac{p}{1-p} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k$$

β_0 = Constant/Intercept,

β_1 and β_k = Coefficient of x_1 Explanatory variables

$(X_1 X_2) p$ = probability of event occurring e.g. willingness participate in e-NAM or not

$\frac{p}{1-p}$ = odd ratio

If probabilities of the event of interest happening for individuals are needed, the

logistic regression equation can be written as (Nitesh, 2018).

$$\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)$$

$$P = 0 < p < 1$$

$$1 - \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)$$

Garret Ranking technique

To find out the constraints faced by the farmers and traders in adopting of e-NAM in Nagpur district of Maharashtra, Garret's ranking

technique was used to rank the constraints faced by them. The respondents were asked to rank the problems faced by them in adopting e-NAM. Then, the ranks given to a constraint by the respondents changed into percent positions by using the following formula:
Percent position = $100 \frac{(R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$

$$\frac{R_{ij} - 0.50}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} is rank given for i th item by j th individual, and N_j is the number of items ranked by j th individual.

The percentage position of each rank is converted into scores by referring table given by Garret. Then for each constraint, the scores of individual respondents are added together and divided by the total number of respondents for whom scores are added. Thus, the mean score for each constraint is ranked by arranging them in descending order.

Results and Discussion

Awareness of Farmers and Traders about e-Nam

Distribution of farmers according to level of awareness about e-NAM

Eight questions were raised to farmers in succession to assess their level of awareness. The Table No.1 shows the distribution of farmers according to level of awareness about e-NAM. The survey results regarding awareness of e-NAM indicate that all respondents (100%) are familiar with the e-NAM platform and acknowledge the necessity of registration before presenting their produce at the APMC. Furthermore, all respondents (100%) report having comprehensive knowledge about e-NAM. However, awareness regarding specific processes within e-NAM varies. Most respondents (78.25%) understand that a Lot ID is assigned to their produce and are aware that assaying follows the generation of this Lot ID. In contrast, 21.75% lack knowledge about these aspects. Awareness about the online circulation of Lot information for bidding is held by 70% of respondents, while 30% are not informed. National online bidding is less widely known, with only 28.75% of respondents aware that bidding occurs across the nation, leaving 71.25% unaware of this process. Additionally, 51.25% of respondents are knowledgeable that payment from the highest bidder is transferred to their account via NEFT, whereas 48.75% are not aware of this payment mechanism.

Distribution of Traders according to level of awareness about e-NAM

Similarly, nine questions were asked to traders in succession to assess their level of awareness. The Table No.2 shows the distribution of farmers according to level of awareness about e-NAM. All 20 respondents (100%) are aware of e-NAM and have a basic understanding of its purpose. They are also uniformly aware that participation requires registration and that a license is necessary for trading. Additionally, all respondents recognize that the license is valid only within a single state. Knowledge about specific features of e-NAM varies significantly. Only 35% of respondents know that online bidding occurs via Smartphone or PC, while 65% are unaware of this aspect. Similarly, 35% understand that logistics are associated with e-NAM for procured entities, whereas 65% do not. Awareness of payment and receipt processes is relatively high. 80% of respondents are aware that the highest bidder pays to e-NAM, and 90% know that the highest bidder receives an online receipt for their procurement.

Overall, while the basic and procedural aspects of e-NAM are well understood, there are notable gaps in awareness regarding online bidding and logistical arrangements.

Willingness to adopt e-NAM by Farmers and Traders

Binary regression (Logit Model) of willingness to adopt e-NAM by farmers

The results of Logit regression indicate that social category, age of respondent, education of respondent and distance from the APMC significantly affected the willingness to participate in e-NAM to sell

their agricultural produce. Table No. 3 indicates that if the age was increased by one year among the respondent, then the probability to participate in e-NAM decreased by 0.87 times. If the education of the farmer has increased then their willingness to participate in e-NAM was increased by 1.29 times.

Independent variables those had significant positive influence on willingness to participate in e-NAM were farmer's social category, age of the respondent, education. Variables those were statistically significant as well as negatively influencing willingness to participate in e-NAM for farmers were age and distance from the APMC.

Binary regression (Logit Model) of willingness to adopt e-NAM by traders

The results of Logit regression indicate that social category, age of the respondent, education, lending money to farmer and number of market function involved in APMC, affected the willing to adopt in e-NAM by traders. Table 4 indicates if the age was increased by one year among the respondent, then the probability to participate in e-NAM decreased by 1.96 times and if the education of the traders has increased then their willingness to participate in e-NAM was increased by 2.87 times. Similarly, when traders were more involved in the function of APMC the probability to participate in e-NAM increased by 27 times.

Independent variables those had significant positive influence on willingness to participate in e-NAM by trader's were social category, education, lending money to farmer and number of functions involved. Business profits were non-significant parameter because traders were afraid that their income will be known.

Constraints Perceived in the Adoption of e-NAM by Farmers and Traders.

Constraints Perceived in the Adoption of e-NAM by Farmers.

Constraints perceived in adoption of e-NAM by farmers were presented in Table 5. Farmers perceive several constraints in adopting e-NAM. The complexity of the sale process is the most significant issue, with a mean score of 72.10. This is followed by inadequate basic infrastructure (mean of 71.51) and difficulties in price realization (mean of 69.78). Challenges in online payment processes also stand out, with a mean of 59.31. Insufficient information transmission (mean of 57.23) and issues with bidding and unsold lots (mean of 46.65) are notable concerns. Preferences for physical presence (mean of 46.21) and shortages of computer operators (mean of 46.05) are also significant, alongside the need for cash payments (mean of 46.05). Managing perishable produce (mean of 42.16) and discomfort with technology (mean of 41.14) are additional barriers. Less critical issues include digital payment barriers (mean of 37.39), lack of assaying laboratories (mean of 36.61), and problems with payment trust (mean of 35.43).

These findings indicate that issues related to the sale process complexity, infrastructure, and payment difficulties are the primary barriers to e-NAM adoption among farmers.

Constraints Perceived in the Adoption of e-NAM by Traders.

The constraints perceived in the adoption of e-NAM by traders are detailed in Table no. 6 indicate that High Transportation Cost (Garrett score 76.95) emerged as the most significant constraint, followed by Technological Illiteracy (Garrett score 68) and Poor Flow of Market Information (Garrett score 66.1). Other major constraints include Lack of Internet Facility (Garrett score 62.5) and Management Problems of Produce Unsold (Garrett score 50). Additionally, Difficulty in Getting License (Garrett score 45) and Invasion by Capital Corporate Houses (Garrett score 41) were also notable concerns. Constraints such as Insufficient Number of Computer Operators (Garrett score 35), Complaint Settlement (Garrett score 28), and the Impact on Small Traders (Garrett score 17) were perceived as less critical.

Overall, high transportation costs and technological challenges had the greatest impact on the adoption of e-NAM among traders.

Table No. 1: Distribution of farmers according to the level of awareness about e-NAM

Sr. No.	Questions on Guttman scale	Awareness (N=80)	
		Yes	No
1	Have you heard about e-NAM?	80 (100)	0 (0)
2	Do you have complete knowledge about e-NAM?	80 (100)	0 (0)
3	Do you know that you have to register before taking your produce in APMC for e-NAM?	80 (100)	0 (0)
4	Do you know that a Lot ID was generated for your produce?	63 (78.25)	17 (21.75)
5	Are you aware that after your Lot ID has been generated, assaying takes place?	63 (78.25)	17 (21.75)
6	Do you know that your Lot information was circulated online for bidding?	56 (70)	24 (30)
7	Do you know that bidding takes place online across nation?	23 (28.75)	57 (71.25)
8	Do you know that highest bidder payment amount was transferred your account through NEFT?	41 (51.25)	39 (48.75)

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table No. 2: Distribution of traders according to the level of awareness about e-NAM

Sr. No.	Question on Guttman scale	Awareness (N=20)	
		Yes	No
1	Have you heard about e-NAM?	20 (100)	0 (0)
2	Do you any idea about e-NAM?	20 (100)	0 (0)
3	Do you know that you have to register before taking part in e- NAM?	20 (100)	0 (0)
4	Do you know that a license needs to be made for trading?	20 (100)	0 (0)
5	Do you know that license was valid in one state only?	20 (100)	0 (0)
6	Do you know that online bidding takes place via Smartphone/PC?	7 (35)	13 (65)
7	Do you know that highest bidder will pay to e-NAM?	16 (80)	4 (20)
8	Do you know about highest bidder will get online receipt for his procurement?	18 (90)	2 (10)
9	Do you know that logistics were associated to e-NAM for procured entity?	7 (35)	13 (65)

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table No. 3: Factors affecting willingness of farmers to adopt e-NAM

Sr. No.	Independent Variable	Parameter Estimate	Standard Error
1	Social category	0.271**	0.678
2	Education	1.292**	0.462
3	Distance from Road APMC	1.779**	0.222
4	Total Family Size	0.824	0.251
5	Age of respondent	0.877**	0.050
6	Income	1.000	4.042

Note: ** Indicate statistically significant at the 5 % level of significance

Table No. 4: Factors affecting willingness of traders to adopt e-NAM

Sr. No.	Independent Variable	Parameter Estimate	Standard Error
1	Social category	6.009**	1.734
2	Education	2.867**	0.213
3	Age of respondent	1.963**	0.528
4	Business turnover	1.003	4.432
5	Lend money of farmers	23.096**	2.342
6	No. Of market function involved	27.173**	3.213

Note: ** Indicate statistically significant at the 5 % level of significance

Table No. 5: Constraints perceived in the adoption of e-NAM by farmers

Sr. No.	Constraints	Sum of Garrett Value	Mean	Rank
1.	Lack of proper information transmission.	4578	57.23	V
2.	e- auction takes much longer than conventional process	3472	43.40	X
3.	Bidding may be not satisfactory and problems regarding unsold lots	3732	46.65	VI
4.	Insufficient number of computer operator	3562	46.05	VIII
5.	Strong trust in physical presence for selling	3697	46.21	VII
6.	Management of perishable produce, especially storage in APMC	3373	42.16	XI
7.	Digital payments were barrier in repayment of informal loans taken	2991	37.39	XIII
8.	No proper assaying laboratory	2929	36.61	XIV
9.	Farmers were uncomfortable using technology/computers	3291	41.14	XII
10.	Problems regarding receiving payments for produce and lack of faith on online transaction	2834	35.43	XV
11.	Difficulties in online payment process	4745	59.31	IV
12.	Lack of basic infrastructure for cleaning, weighing etc.	5721	71.51	II
13.	Sale process was complicated	5768	72.10	1
14.	Price realization was difficult	5582	69.78	III
15.	Farmers need cash payment to meet immediate expenses	3684	46.05	VIII

Table No. 6: Constraints perceived in the adoption of e-NAM by Traders

Sr. No.	Constraints	Sum of Garrett Value	Mean	Rank
1.	High Transportation cost	1539	76.95	I
2.	Safeness of Insurance for the product sold in the market or warehouse	1229	61.45	V
3.	Complaint settlement maybe awkward	560	28	X
4.	Poor flow of market information	1322	66.1	III
5.	Business of small traders badly affected	340	17	XI
6.	Invasion by Capital Corporate Houses	820	41	VIII
7.	Lack of internet facility	1250	62.5	IV
8.	Technological illiteracy	1360	68	II
9.	Management problems of produce unsold	1000	50	VI

10.	Insufficient number of computer operator	700	35	IX
11.	Difficulty in getting license	900	45	VII

Conclusion

The performance of the e-NAM (National Agriculture Market) platform in Nagpur district reveals a mixed landscape of awareness, adoption, and constraints among farmers and traders. Both groups generally recognize e-NAM's basic functions, such as the need for registration, but there is uneven understanding of more detailed aspects. While 100% of farmers and traders are aware of e-NAM, only a fraction of farmers knows about nationwide bidding, and many traders lack knowledge about online bidding and logistics. Willingness to adopt e-NAM varies: younger and more educated farmers are more inclined to participate, whereas older individuals and those farther from APMC centers are less likely to do so. For traders, education and involvement in APMC functions boost adoption, while older traders and those less engaged are less likely to adopt the platform. Key constraints include the complexity of the sales process, inadequate infrastructure, and difficulties with online payments for farmers, and high transportation costs, technological illiteracy, and poor market information for traders. To improve e-NAM's effectiveness, targeted educational programs, better infrastructure, and supportive policies are necessary. Future research should investigate the long-term impacts of e-NAM, the effectiveness of interventions to address adoption barriers, and the platform's overall influence on market dynamics and farmer incomes.

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